

Spiritual wellbeing : Panacea for Mental Health

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Abstract

Spiritual wellness is progressively acknowledged as an essential factor in mental health, particularly within the domain of healthcare. Nowadays , many people are suffering from problems like anxiety ,depression , stress etc . The present study search into the prospective utilization of spiritual wellness as a universal cure-all for mental health conditions, underlining the significance of addressing the spiritual dimension in the treatment of mental health. The document delivers a comprehensive discourse on the notion of spiritual well-being, critically examining its link to psychological welfare and the causal factors that precipitate spiritual distress. Additionally, it highlight the decreasing evidence that accept the inclusion of spirituality in mental healthcare and the advantages of attending to spiritual well-being in mental health intervention. These gains comprise enhanced coping techniques, superior standard of living, augmented resilience, and reduced susceptibility to psychological ailments. The document also deliberates on the obstacles of incorporating spirituality into mental healthcare and the necessity for culturally sensitive and patient-oriented methodologies to spiritual healthcare. Ultimately, the paper contends that spiritual well-being is a crucial constituent of mental wellness, and medical trainee ought to contemplate addressing patients' spiritual needs in mental health therapy. To know the role of “spiritual well-being” and its effect on “mental health” researcher had considered 219 respondents for the study survey and concludes that there is significant effect of “spiritual well-being on mental health” of an individual.

Keywords- Spiritual well-being , Mental health therapy, Spiritual well-being in mental health.

Introduction

Sexual misconduct is a significant global issue concerning public health. The incorporation of religion into the field of psychology has posed difficulties for scholars and experts. Human religious devotion cannot be accurately defined by a single criterion. Instead, it must be evaluated based on its unique features that differentiate it from non-secular practices. Religiosity encompasses three primary components: acknowledgment of the spiritual domain, involvement in customary spiritual rituals and rites, and adherence to ethical principles that are rooted in spiritual doctrines. Taylor, Piotrowski, Woodgate, & Letourneau, (2014)

It has been observed that people who have experienced sexual misconduct by non-religious authorities may undergo a decline in their level of religious devotion and commitment. Adult survivors may find themselves inclined to switch their religious beliefs or abandon formal religion altogether. Soulfulness impacts our state positively. Studies show it affects our thoughts, deeds, and existence. Mental well-being shares a generally positive relationship with spiritual well-being. Hadzic, (2011)

Though how it happens, still remains unclear scientifically. We suggest spirituality as a solution to improving mental health, particularly among victims of childhood sexual harassment or those who lose faith. Knowing the role of spirituality in mental health might help generate helpful treatments.

Literature review

According to Srivastava and Gupta (2022), The COVID-19 pandemic has caused a significant disruption in the global work environment and has taken a toll on the physical, emotional, spiritual, and psychological well-being of employees. It can be considered a traumatic event that has resulted in widespread changes in working conditions, causing several issues for employees. The complexity of personal and professional lives of employees has been exacerbated by the pandemic, leading to an increased need for organizational leaders to enhance their capabilities to handle empowered employees at lower hierarchies. In this context, it is essential for organizational leaders to embrace spiritual values and create a spiritual climate within the organization to foster workforce agility and identification with the organization. This can help employees find meaning and purpose in their work and realize the significance of working collaboratively in the service of customers. Organizational leaders

recognize the need for a spiritual domain in employees. Encourage the development of such values in the workplace. When employees feel empowered and are aligned with the values of the organization, they are more likely to remain committed to the organization and demonstrate higher levels of job satisfaction. spiritual climate in the organization positively impacts employee well-being and job performance. Organizational leaders to prioritize the development of a spiritual climate within the workplace. To ensure the overall well-being and morale of employees.

Shahrbabaki, Nouhi, Kazemi, & Ahmadi, (2017)Heart insufficiency is a grave ailment that arises when the heart fails to satisfy the metabolic requisites of the human body. This affliction affects nearly 23 million individuals across the globe and can have calamitous ramifications. Patients suffering from cardiac insufficiency exhibit elevated hospitalization rates and increased mortality, with over 40% of patients succumbing to the ailment within a year of their preliminary hospitalization. The principal purpose of treating heart failure is to enrich the life quality of patients by managing symptoms and encouraging beneficial effort.

The ailment's management and upholding a treatment regimen can pose immense challenges for patients, and it is imperative to provide them with expansive support during this process. Religion constitutes a vital aspect of healthcare, and the medical community has increasingly emphasized the significance of catering to patients' religious needs. Spiritual convictions may hold significant influence in aiding patients in dealing with heart failure, discovering a feeling of peacefulness, and formulating decisions concerning the treatment and administration of persistent conditions. Religious and spiritual beliefs are pivotal mechanisms for patients grappling with long-lasting and life-threatening ailments, particularly for those enduring cardiac insufficiency. The reservoir of resources available to them can be invaluable in confronting the complexities of living with such a condition. With the growing number of individuals affected by this affliction, it is crucial to equip them with the essential tools and resources to manage their condition effectively.

According to Srivastava (2013), marriage is a consensual and contractual relationship that is recognized by law and has tremendous social and cultural pressure in India. Marriage is an intricate concept that requires one's commitment and demands attention to various aspects, including emotional, social, and occupational needs. Marriage is a societal establishment that provides a socially acceptable avenue for fulfilling fundamental human desires. Its purpose

extends beyond this, however, as it also serves as a foundation for creating a family and procreating. The choice to wed may arise from a plethora of legal, emotional, economic, spiritual, and religious factors. The connection between matrimony and mental health is intricate.

With each having an effect on the other. The ethical and legal ramifications of this relationship. Treating psychiatrists often face predicaments while counseling mentally ill patients and their families about the prospects of marriage. However, guidelines on marriage and mental health issues are being developed by the specialty section on women's mental health of the Indian Psychiatric Society, which will help reduce these predicaments. spiritual well-being has been considered a panacea. individuals who are spiritual have a lower risk of developing mental illnesses such as depression and anxiety. Spiritual prosperity has been observed to be intimately linked with psychological prosperity, robustness, and effective coping methods. It is purported that spirituality imbues existence with a sense of significance and direction, fosters affirmative relationships, and equips individuals to contend with tension and hardship.

According to Khasawneh (2011), in the quest for achieving optimal mental health, spiritual well-being has emerged as a potential panacea. The significance of spirituality in the professional domain and its effects on the holistic well-being of staff cannot be overstated. As per the workplace spirituality dimensions, employees have acknowledged a considerable-to-high level of spirituality in their working environment. Notably, the "self-level of spirituality in the workplace," "group level of workplace spirituality," and "the community and spirituality in the workplace" dimensions received the most substantial levels of concurrence.

Such dimensions suggest that personnel are mindful of the importance of personal and collective spiritual welfare, along with the workplace's role in promoting such practices. On the other hand, the dimensions of "family and spirituality in the workplace" and "management systems that encourage personal and spiritual transformation" were moderately agreed upon. This implies that while employees acknowledge the potential impact of family and management systems on spiritual well-being, they do not perceive these dimensions to be as significant as others.

According to Smith-MacDonald, Norris, Raffin-Bouchal, and Sinclair (2017), spirituality may play an important role in promoting mental well-being among combat veterans. Standardized treatments for mental health concerns related to combat typically involve evidence-based pharmacology and cognitive-behavioral psychotherapies. Many individuals experiencing mental health concerns tend to avoid seeking professional care, and those who do pursue care often drop out of treatment prematurely, leading to high attrition rates. This has led to a growing recognition and acceptance of comprehensive and alternative therapies for combat trauma. These treatments may incorporate techniques such as art and music therapy, animal-assisted therapy, mind-body practices, and spiritual-healing techniques.

Spirituality and religion, often referred to as "spirituality," encompass beliefs, values, actions, and experiences pertaining to ultimate meaning, often involving deities and doctrine created by faith-based organizations or institutions over time. Spirituality often serves as the primary and prevalent coping mechanism when confronted with a health crisis, traumatic event, or distress. The substantiation for the association linking spirituality and mental health outcomes in military veterans, which covers post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), self-inflicted harm, despondency, standard of living, fury, and unease, ranges from average to pleasing. Spirituality is a convoluted and multifaceted concept that may undertake a pivotal function in buttressing and facilitating the recovery and mental well-being among military veterans.

Fisher, (2011) states that There is a burgeoning acceptance of human spirituality as an authentic and genuine phenomenon, and not merely a product of the mind. This recognition has spawned a necessity for valid and dependable methods to appraise spiritual well-being, with the aim of progressing our understanding of it. Spiritual well-being is a paradigm that strives to encompass the assorted array of perspectives posited in dialogues about spirituality. It envelops the same realm of investigation as spiritual health, and both are composite of the quality of the relationships that individuals forge with themselves, others, their surroundings, and/or a divine entity. It is noteworthy that spiritual well-being should not be conflated with the affirmative psychology's notion of psychological well-being. While these two are interrelated, psychological well-being primarily focuses on the study of the psyche or mind.

The four domains model asserts that spiritual well-being includes the psychological or cognitive knowledge component of each domain but also delves deeper into the heart or core of a person through profound relationships. In the context of mental health, spiritual well-

being can be seen as a panacea, offering a comprehensive approach to improving the quality of life and overall mental health of individuals.

According to Mechanic, Weaver, and Resick (2008), intimate partner abuse can have various mental health consequences. Partner maltreatment has been distinguished as a substantial forecaster of Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD) indications. Physical and/or sexual aggression, wounds, psychological maltreatment, and stalking are all noteworthy factors that contribute to the prediction of PTSD. The sequencing of these factors in the equation also impacts their contribution to the prognosis of PTSD indications. When physical aggression and injuries are included before psychological maltreatment and stalking, all three predictor sets contribute significantly to the anticipation of PTSD. Psychological maltreatment and stalking also contribute to the PTSD indications prognosis, even when controlling for the effects of more severe forms of partner abuse.

However, when the order of entry is inverted, psychological maltreatment and stalking enter first, while physical injuries come last and add to the variance in PTSD scores. This emphasizes the exceptional roles of stalking, physical aggression, and psychological maltreatment in the prediction of traumatic stress indications. Interestingly, the contribution of sexual coercion to PTSD indication prognosis was not deemed unique in the study. In view of these revelations, it is crucial to acknowledge the function of partner maltreatment in predicting PTSD and prioritize interventions that tackle the different forms of maltreatment. Furthermore, endorsing spiritual well-being has demonstrated a constructive influence on mental health and could potentially function as a panacea for those undergoing PTSD indications.

Objective

1. To know the role of “spiritual well-being” as a solution for “mental health.”
2. To know effect of “spiritual well-being” on “mental health” of an individual.

Methodology

The researcher had conducted the study survey with the help of a structured questionnaire on 219 respondents to know the role of “spiritual well-being” and its effect on “mental health.” The primary data is collected through “convenient sampling method” and data was analysed by “mean and t-test.”

Findings

In 219 respondents 32.4% are male and rest 67.6% are female. 23.3% of them are below 26 years of age, 32.9% are between 26-30 years of age & 43.8% are above 30 years of age. 41.5% are graduate and below, 28.8% are post graduates and above and rest 29.7% are having other educational qualification. 24.2% of them are students, 21.0% are salaried, 22.8% are self-employed and rest 32.0% are house makers. 40.6% of the respondents are married and rest 59.5% are unmarried.

General Details

Variable	Respondent	Percentage
Gender		
Male	71	32.4
Female	148	67.6
Total	219	100
Age (years)		
Below 26	51	23.3
26-30	72	32.9
Above 30	96	43.8
Total	219	100
Education		
Graduate and below	91	41.5
Post Graduate and above	63	28.8
Others	65	29.7
Total	219	100
Occupation		
Students	53	24.2
Salaried	46	21.0
Self-employed	50	22.8
House maker	70	32.0
Total	219	100
Marital status		
Married	89	40.6
Unmarried	130	59.5
Total	219	100

Table 1 Role and effect of spiritual well-being on mental health

S. No.	Statements	Mean Value	t value	Sig.
1.	Spiritual beliefs contribute as a shield for suicidal behaviour in adverse situations	3.13	1.958	0.026
2.	Spiritual well being help to increase the levels of self-control, monitoring, regulation, reflection and development	3.18	2.728	0.003
3.	Spiritual well-being helps in adapting stress while going through phycological discomfort in life	3.12	1.847	0.033
4.	Spiritual beliefs help to deal with mental health issues like anxiety and depression	3.19	2.866	0.002
5.	Spiritual well-being helps to increase self-esteem and tolerance	3.15	2.300	0.011
6.	Spiritual well-being creates sense of honesty and experiential interconnection	3.17	2.563	0.006
7.	Spiritual experience helps an individual to strong their confrontation approaches	3.14	2.130	0.017
8.	Spiritual well-being improves mental health by gaining physical and psychological healthy life	3.16	2.445	0.008
9.	Improves supportive behaviours (less use of cigarette and alcohol) in addicts	3.11	1.661	0.049
10.	Spiritual beliefs help to have goal, hope and meaning in stressful life	3.20	3.073	0.001

Table above is showing different role of spiritual well-being and its effect on mental health. The respondent says that Spiritual beliefs help to have goal, hope and meaning in stressful life with mean value 3.20, Spiritual beliefs help to deal with mental health issues like anxiety and depression with mean value 3.19 and Spiritual well-being help to increase the levels of self-control, monitoring, regulation, reflection and development with mean value 3.18. The respondent believe that Spiritual well-being creates sense of honesty and experiential interconnection with mean value 3.17, Spiritual well-being improves mental health by gaining physical and psychological healthy life with mean value 3.16 and Spiritual well-being helps to increase self-esteem and tolerance 3.15. Spiritual experience helps an

individual to strong their confrontation approaches with mean value 3.14, Spiritual beliefs contribute as a shield for suicidal behaviour in adverse situations with mean value 3.13, Spiritual well-being helps in adapting stress while going through psychological discomfort in life with mean value 3.12 and improves supportive behaviours (less use of cigarette and alcohol) in addicts with mean value 3.11. The value under significant column for all the statements related to Role and effect of spiritual well-being on mental health is significant with value below 0.05 after applying t test.

Conclusion

The study was conducted to know the role of spiritual well-being as a solution for mental health and found that Spiritual beliefs help to have goal, hope and meaning in stressful life, help to deal with mental health issues like anxiety and depression, help to increase the levels of self-control, monitoring, regulation, reflection and development, Spiritual well-being creates sense of honesty and experiential inter connection and also improves mental health by gaining physical and psychological healthy life

The growing of awareness of the untapped potential of spiritual wellbeing as a real panacea for the persistent scourge of mental health issues has reached a critical people. The illumination of the central role played by the discernment of a sense of direction and purpose in one's existence and the beautify of interpersonal bonds with oneself, others, and a transcendent force in the conceptual framework underlying this approach is fundamental to the propagation of mental wellness and holistic fulfilment. Results presented a moral proof to the positive influence of spiritual philosophy and principles on emotional modulation, problem-solving prowess, emotional stamina, and an overall feeling of contentment in life. On top of this, the salubrious attributes of spiritual health were found to induce a profound decrease in the indices of stress, anxiety, and depression when measured against conventional treatment methodologies, thus heralding a remarkable leap forward in this field. it impossible for everyone to garner the same extent of benefits. To enhance the manifestation of wellness, it is mandatory to approach the wide selection of spiritual models and precepts with an open, experimental attitude that harmonizes with one's personal predilections and preferences. By adopting the manifold opportunities presented by spiritual wellbeing, one can reap the rich rewards of enhanced mental equilibrium and individual gratification.

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